

Rational thinking about rational belief

R. Willink

Abstract

In applied probability and statistics, the concept of ‘rational degree of belief’ about a constant θ is the concept that for a set of information about θ there is a unique probability distribution to attribute to θ . While this concept might not be accepted or discussed greatly in the statistical community, it has some popularity amongst applied scientists. The premise that such a distribution exists for every well-defined set of information about θ is shown to admit a logical contradiction. The logical combination of disjoint sets of information leads to a probability distribution that is a logarithmic pool with every exponent equal to unity. But this implies a rational belief that is not invariant to a non-linear transformation from θ to a different quantity of interest $\lambda = g(\theta)$. The conclusion to be drawn is that, as a universal idea, the concept of rational belief is unsound. This result recently been described in the metrology literature (*Measurement Sensors*, 24, 100416, 2022), where the idea of ‘information as probability’ seems implied in some international guidelines.

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**Robin Willink
Wellington, New Zealand
robin.willink@otago.ac.nz**

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University of Otago,
Wellington, New Zealand
robin.willink@otago.ac.nz

Abstract

In applied probability and statistics, the concept of ‘rational degree of belief’ about a constant θ is the concept that for a set of information about θ there is a unique probability distribution to attribute to θ . While this concept might not be accepted or discussed greatly in the statistical community, it has some popularity amongst applied scientists. The premise that such a distribution exists for every well-defined set of information about θ is shown to admit a logical contradiction. The logical combination of disjoint sets of information leads to a probability distribution that is a logarithmic pool with every exponent equal to unity. But this implies a rational belief that is not invariant to a non-linear transformation from θ to a different quantity of interest $\lambda = g(\theta)$. The conclusion to be drawn is that, as a universal idea, the concept of rational belief is unsound. This result recently been described in the metrology literature (*Measurement Sensors*, 24, 100416, 2022), where the idea of ‘information as probability’ seems implied in some international guidelines.

Keywords: combination of data, information, logarithmic opinion pool, logical probability, objective Bayesian statistics

1. Introduction

There are two contrasting understandings of the idea of ‘degree of belief’ about constants in applied probability and Bayesian statistics. In one, the strength of belief is acknowledged to be personal to the individual, with analysis then involving the idea of ‘subjective probability’ about the unknown quantity of interest, say θ . In another, the belief is understood to be the belief of a rational agent, which is mandated by the information available about θ . As such, it is often called ‘rational belief’, and it might be associated with the notion of ‘logical probability’ or ‘necessary probability’. In the first situation, the probability distribution assigned to θ is an attribute of the person for whom the analysis is being carried out, but in the second situation, it is an attribute of the set of information. The two positions differ qualitatively, meaning that they cannot be called extremes on a single continuum: there can be no middle ground. As a consequence, the validities of these two positions are to be considered separately.

In this paper, we focus on the second understanding, which has some popularity amongst those applied scientists who wish to take a Bayesian position on data analysis. We consider the premise that a set of information about an unknown θ implies a certain pdf for θ , and we obtain a logical contradiction that shows this premise to be false. This contradiction has recently been described in the metrology literature (Willink, 2022), where there has been debate about the appropriate statistical paradigm to employ in the expression of measurement uncertainty. We also consider weaker forms of the premise, and we demonstrate that the only piece of information for which the idea of rational belief applies is knowledge of a frequency distribution underlying the origin of θ .

The field of measurement in the physical sciences is known as *metrology*. In metrology, a measurement is regarded as being incomplete without a statement of ‘measurement uncertainty’. The *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (BIPM *et al*, 1993) affectionately known as ‘the GUM’, is the international standard document, but it is known to mix frequentist and Bayesian ideas in an inappropriate way, (e.g., Gleser, 1998; Kacker and Jones, 2003; Willink, 2013). The task of maintaining the GUM has been given to a group of scientists (Working Group 1 of the Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology) coordinated by the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM). This group initially produced Supplement 1 to the GUM (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2008), which takes a quasi-Bayesian position, thereby commencing the revision of the GUM along Bayesian lines, (e.g., Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2009). The material does not clearly differentiate or explain the contrasting Bayesian positions outlined in the first paragraph here, though references to ‘information’ and ‘state-of-knowledge’ indicate that an objective approach is intended. For example, in explaining the basis of the proposed revision, members of the group write that “Knowledge of all quantities in the proposals is represented by probability distributions” (Bich *et al*, 2016, sec. 3.1) and

that the definition of standard uncertainty in the proposals is “standard deviation of the random variable describing the state of knowledge about a quantity” (Bich *et al*, 2016, sec. 3.2) So the impersonal idea of information or knowledge is emphasized more than the personal idea of belief or opinion. Thus, we read: (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2008, Introduction),

The PDF for a quantity expresses the state of knowledge about the quantity, i.e. it quantifies the degree of belief about the values that can be assigned to the quantity based on the available information.

Here the reader of the document — typically a physicist, chemist or engineer — seems encouraged to conclude that a probability density function (PDF or pdf) for an unknown, say θ , accords with a set of information or a body of knowledge about θ .

The essential idea is that of information implying probability. This is expressed clearly by Sivia in the more general context of data analysis (Sivia, 1996, pp. 9,10):

The popular argument goes that if a probability represents a degree-of-belief then it must be subjective because my belief could be different from yours. The Bayesian view is that a probability does indeed represent how much we believe that something is true, but that this belief should be based on all the relevant information available. ... As Jaynes has pointed out, objectivity demands only that two people having the same information should assign the same probability; this principle has played a key role in the modern development of the (objective) Bayesian approach.

So objective Bayesian statistics replaces the idea of subjective belief by one of ‘rational’ belief. This accords with the idea of *logical probability*, where a probability is seen as an objective degree to which one proposition implies another (Barnett, 1973).

To argue against this point of view logically, we must identify it using terms that permit analysis. Therefore, we begin by stating the essential premise of the idea of ‘rational belief’. We consider this premise to be:

P: To any set of information S about an unknown constant θ , there is a unique probability density function $f_S(x)$ corresponding to rational belief about θ .

If we accept this premise then we can consider the pdf $f_S(x)$ to be an objective attribute of S . We could then use P to say simply “The probability density function of θ associated with a set of information S is $f_S(x)$.” Having stated this premise clearly, we can subject it to examination. We will demonstrate that P is self-contradictory and that therefore it must be false. In the method of argument, the function $f_S(x)$ will be assumed known, but the conclusion that we reach does not require this.

Section 2 deals with the combination of probability distributions for the same quantity, which has relevance in metrology because of the importance of inter-laboratory measurement comparisons, as will be explained. The distribution obtained is notable in its own right, but its significance here is that it leads to a simple internal inconsistency. Section 3 describes this inconsistency, which is the contradiction that shows premise P to be false. Section 4 contains discussion and analysis of weaker forms of the premise.

2. The combination of unrelated objective distributions

2.1. Derivation of the logarithmic pool

Our analysis involves a thought experiment. Suppose that a scientist has unrelated sets of information about unknowns θ_1 and θ_2 , both of which exist on a discrete scale with unit of resolution δ and with potential values $\dots -2\delta, -\delta, 0, \delta, 2\delta \dots$. In accordance with (the discrete analogue of) P, the scientist attributes to θ_1 and θ_2 the appropriate probability mass functions (pmfs) $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$. Because the sets of information are unrelated, i.e., disjoint, the bivariate quantity (θ_1, θ_2) is considered to have pmf

$$\Pr(\theta_1 = x_1 \cap \theta_2 = x_2) = p_1(x_1) p_2(x_2),$$

as seen in Figure 1(a) for $\delta = 1$ and for $(p_1(1), p_1(2), p_1(3), p_1(4), p_1(5)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2)$ and $(p_2(2), p_2(3), p_2(4), p_2(5), p_2(6)) = (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1)$. Imagine that the scientist then receives the new piece of information that θ_1 and θ_2 are equal. The condition $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ applies and the single unknown can be relabelled θ . By the definition of conditional probability, $\Pr(A|B) \equiv \Pr(A \cap B) / \Pr(B)$, the pmf attributable to θ must be

$$p(x) \equiv \Pr(\theta = x) = \frac{p_1(x) p_2(x)}{\sum_z p_1(z) p_2(z)}, \quad (1)$$

as depicted in Figure 1(b) for the unconditional distribution of Figure 1(a). The final set of information about θ does not depend on whether the scientist learns that $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ before or after the two sets of information are considered together, so (1) must be the pmf that results when combining two unrelated pmfs $p_1(x)$ and $p_2(x)$ for the single quantity θ .

Figure 1: (a) Example joint probability mass function $\Pr(\hat{\theta}_1 = x_1 \cap \hat{\theta}_2 = x_2)$ with $\delta = 1$. (b) Corresponding probability mass function on the condition that $\hat{\theta}_1 = \hat{\theta}_2$. (Empty cells have mass zero.)

Equation (1) can be written as

$$\frac{p(x)}{\delta} = \frac{p_1(x)/\delta \times p_2(x)/\delta}{\sum_z p_1(z)/\delta \times p_2(z)/\delta \times \delta}. \quad (2)$$

As the unit of resolution δ is reduced to zero, $\hat{\theta}$ becomes a quantity θ on the real line, $p_j(\cdot)/\delta$ and $p(\cdot)/\delta$ become pdfs $f_j(\cdot)$ and $f(\cdot)$, and the sum becomes an integral. We obtain the equation

$$f(x) = \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x)}{\int f_1(z)f_2(z) dz} \quad (3)$$

as the unique equation describing the result whenever two independently-formed objective pdfs for a single quantity are to be logically combined (Willink, 2022). This equation describes a logarithmic pool with every exponent equal to unity (e.g., Genest and Zidek, 1986). It should not be understood to be a *logarithmic opinion pool*, which relates to opinions, not information.

In the metrology literature, this result was derived in the context of obtaining the best estimate of the unknown value of an artefact (say a mass) circulated to laboratories participating in a ‘measurement

comparison’ (Willink, 2006). The proper assessment of the abilities of the participating laboratories to make measurements depends on the fidelity of their measurement estimate to the best estimate obtained by the group of laboratories. Some international guidelines (see Section 1) appear to suggest that the submission of the j th laboratory is to be a pdf $f_j(x)$ for the unknown value, so that the combination of such pdfs becomes logically mandated. When there are two contributions, equation (3) results. The mode of derivation of the result in the original paper (Willink, 2006) did not involve discrete variables, which opened it to a legitimate criticism involving Borel’s paradox (Grientschnig and Lira, 2014). The device of discretizing and passing in the limit to continuous variables employed here overcomes that criticism (Willink, 2019, 2021, 2022).

We now make the identity of the quantity explicit by writing $f_\theta(x)$, $f_{\theta,1}(x)$ and $f_{\theta,2}(x)$ instead of $f(x)$, $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$, to obtain the basic result

$$f_\theta(x) = \frac{f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x)}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_{\theta,1}(z)f_{\theta,2}(z) dz} \quad (4)$$

for the combination of two objective pdfs for θ . By the fully *deductive* argument irresponsibly known as “mathematical *induction*”, the result is easily extended to apply with a larger number of disjoint sets of information about θ : we simply collect and process the sets of information one at a time. Thus, we have the following result for $m \geq 1$. If $f_{\theta,j}$ is the pdf that corresponds to the j th disjoint set of information about θ then the pdf that corresponds to the union of the m sets of information is

$$f_\theta(x) = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^m f_{\theta,j}(x)}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^m f_{\theta,j}(z) dz}. \quad (5)$$

However, as described in Section 3, these results admit a simple logical contradiction.

2.2. *Disjointness and independence*

Before proceeding, let us clarify the idea of unrelated or disjoint sets of information, or independently-formed pdfs, which seemed to be misunderstood in different ways by reviewers of some the author’s contributions to the metrological literature (Willink, 2021, Appendix; Willink, 2024).

The concept of disjoint of sets of information is the concept of disjointness found in set theory: there is no piece of information that is contained in both sets. Equivalently, if any piece of information in one set is found to be faulty – so that it ceases to qualify as information at all — then this does not affect the other set of information in any way. This does not mean that the pdfs claimed to correspond to these disjoint sets of information will have disjoint regions of support. Yet one reviewer appeared to confuse these two ideas.

Another reviewer imagined (a) assigning independent Gaussian distributions to the coefficients of thermal expansion, θ_1 and θ_2 , of two blocks made from carbon stainless steel using data from a (metallurgical) reference book and then (b) learning that the two blocks came from the same batch of material, so that it became known that $\theta_1 \approx \theta_2$. Quite reasonably, the reviewer felt that multiplying the Gaussian pdfs, as in (3), would be inappropriate in this case, because the standard deviation would wrongly be reduced. But (3) does not apply in this case because, although they were treated as the distributions of independent variables before it was learned that $\theta_1 \approx \theta_2$, the contributing distributions were formed from the same information, which was the data in the same reference book. The ‘distributions were independent’ but the distributions were not independently-formed: the sets of information giving rise to the distributions were not disjoint.

In this author’s experience, these misconceptions are indicative of those that many applied scientists have about statistical theory, especially scientists who have difficulty recognising and accepting the vast conceptual difference between frequentist and Bayesian statistics. They are evidence that the statistical literature must clearly articulate basic ideas and concepts to graduates in other quantitative fields.

The following trivial example illustrates the idea of disjoint sets of information. Imagine that a company manufactures spherical ball bearings and that the diameter of one particular bearing is to be estimated. The diameter is measured on a unbiased device known to have normally distributed error with standard deviation 0.2 mm. The estimate obtained is 9.7 mm. According to some principle, perhaps an informal understanding, perhaps the idea of a flat prior distribution, perhaps the idea of fiducial probability or perhaps the idea of maximum entropy, the analyst uses this information to attribute the diameter a normal distribution with mean 9.7 mm and standard deviation 0.2 mm, regarding this as being objective or rational. A second analyst measures the diameter of the ball bearing by a different technique known to incur exponentially related error with lower limit 0 mm and mean 0.1 mm. The estimate obtained is 9.8 mm. By some principle, both analysts agree that — by itself — this second set of information would enable them to rationally attribute the value of θ the distribution of $(9.8 - 0.1Y)$ millimetres where Y has the standard exponential distribution. The two sets of information are disjoint: any alteration to a figure in one would have no impact on the other, so $f_1(x)$ is the pdf of a normal variable with mean 9.7 mm and standard deviation 0.2 mm and $f_2(x)$ is the pdf of $(9.8 - 0.1Y)$ millimetres. Equation (3) is then applicable.

3. A contradiction

Let us return to our original context of $m = 2$. Suppose that $\lambda \equiv g(\theta)$ is a potential quantity of interest and that g describes a monotonic non-linear transformation. (For example, we might be interested in

estimating the volume of the ball bearing rather than the diameter, in which case $\lambda = \pi\theta^3/6$.) We know that

$$f_\lambda(y) = f_\theta(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right| \quad y \equiv g(x), \quad (6)$$

because g is monotonic. When this transformation is applied with the pdf formed in (4) we obtain

$$f_\lambda(y) \propto f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (7)$$

but when the transformation is applied to the contributing pdfs *before* combining the resulting pdfs $f_{\lambda,1}(y)$ and $f_{\lambda,2}(y)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f_\lambda(y) &\propto f_{\lambda,1}(y)f_{\lambda,2}(y) \\ &= f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The right-hand sides of (7) and (8) describe different pdfs, because $g(x)$ is non-linear. So updating before transforming and transforming before updating, both of which are permitted, lead to different results. Thus, we have obtained different results when applying two correct methods that should have given the same result. And if we subsequently apply the inverse transformation to recover a pdf for θ then (7) and (8) give, respectively,

$$f_\theta(x) \propto f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \quad (9)$$

$$f_\theta(x) \propto f_{\theta,1}(x)f_{\theta,2}(x) \left| \frac{dx}{dy} \right|, \quad (10)$$

which differ.

4. Implications and weaker premises

The analysis above has shown that the pdf (4) is logically implied when combining pdfs $f_{\theta,1}(x)$ and $f_{\theta,2}(x)$ said to accurately represent disjoint sets of information about the same quantity, θ . Yet, when this result is applied in an analysis involving a non-linear function g , we can correctly obtain two different pdfs for the quantity $\lambda \equiv g(\theta)$, as in (7) and (8). Equivalently, simply by involving an arbitrary non-linear function g , we can correctly obtain different pdfs for the original quantity θ , as in (9) and (10). Yet premise P states that there is a *unique* pdf corresponding to any set of information about a quantity. The only possible conclusion is that P is incorrect. Premise P with the additional premise that $f_\theta(x)$ is known would represent the starting point of any complete objective Bayesian

theory. Thus, the objective Bayesian ideal, P, is an illusion.

(There is a much simpler demonstration that P is false, but the argument seems to have lost force. If P holds then it holds for the set of information corresponding to knowledge that a quantity lies in the interval $[0, 1]$. But this set of information for a quantity θ is the same as the set of information for $\sqrt{\theta}$. So both θ and $\sqrt{\theta}$ must be attributed the same probability distribution. Clearly this is illogical — unless we admit an ‘improper distribution’ from which actual probabilities cannot be calculated.)

It might be suggested that P overstates the relevant premise: perhaps we should instead consider the weaker premise that “a known pdf can provide an *approximate* representation of a set of information”. But this statement would need greater clarity. If it implies the existence of *unknown* pdfs that would represent the sets of information exactly then the logical contradiction applies with those pdfs: the fact that they are unknown is not relevant. On the other hand, if it means that a pdf only represents a set of information *partially* then the statement fails to have any substantial meaning. This would invalidate a claim such as (Possolo, 2015)

Measurement uncertainty is described *fully* and quantitatively by a probability distribution on the set of values of the measurand.

(Italicization added here.)

A naive alternative objection might be that, in practice, people do not actually have independent sets of information. If true, this claim would not invalidate the conclusion — because the conclusion relates to logic, not practice.

The contradiction shows that P is false, meaning that *not every* set of information has an associated pdf. However, that does not mean that there are no sets of information that would lead to a pdf describing rational belief. So let us weaken premise P to:

P': For any unknown constant θ there is at least one potential set of information for which there is a unique probability density function corresponding to rational belief about θ .

To assess this premise, consider knowing only that θ was randomly selected from a distribution described by the pdf $f(x)$, as might be the case in our example if the ball-bearing was taken from a production line with known long-run behaviour. Then, if you believe and want to apply P', the only rational thing to do is to see $f(x)$ as describing your belief about θ . Now the contradiction shows that if two sets of information imply rational pdfs for θ then these sets cannot be disjoint. It follows that *there can be no information about θ admitting a rational pdf unless the information involves this frequency distribution in some way*. This holds whether or not there is such a frequency distribution, because the conclusion can be reached in a thought experiment. Thus, the general concept of ‘rational belief’ implying a pdf must be discarded.

4. Conclusion

A Bayesian approach to analysis must use probability to represent either (a) an honest degree of personal belief or (b) a mandated degree of ‘rational belief’. These possibilities are incompatible: either a probability distribution for a constant quantity θ is (a) an attribute of the person claiming the probability distribution or (b) an attribute of the information available. There is no acceptable, informal, middle ground.

In this paper, the view promoting a universal principle of rational belief as probability has been shown to imply a logical contradiction, this contradiction appearing in the standard scientific problem when sets of information for the same quantity θ are combined. Straightforward analysis shows that when two or more disjoint sets of information with associated pdfs $\{f_j(x)\}$ are combined the resulting pdf is proportional to the product $\prod_j f_j(x)$, as in (5). But the application of a non-linear transformation of variables before and after the combination of pdfs leads to different results, which implies a logical inconsistency. The logical conclusion is that probability as rational belief is not a universally valid concept.

Subsequently, we can envisage being told that the quantity of interest was drawn from a known frequency distribution. Straightforward argument shows that any set of information that implies a particular probability distribution must involve this frequency distribution. Thus the concept of probability as rational belief seems limited to a frequency-based paradigm.

The conclusion that ‘rational belief’ does not imply probability be no surprise to many statisticians reading this article. Yet the message that the theory of probability cannot be used in this way has not permeated the communities of applied scientists sufficiently, as is exemplified in the discussions surrounding the evaluation of measurement uncertainty alluded to in Section 1. It is important for the statistical community to provide clear messages to others about the validity and applicability of different concepts featuring in probability and statistics. Accordingly, this paper is written to demonstrate that the idea of associating rational belief with probability is untenable in scientific work.

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